

Rapid calculation of the number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds in aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons

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Abstract : The newly proposed formulae to calculate the number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds of aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons from the molecular formulae of organic molecules is a vitally important tool for students of chemistry at undergraduate and graduate level for solving different kinds of problems regarding different chemical reactions. In this manuscript the suggested bonds can be calculated from the molecular formulae as well as from any structural representation of a molecule corresponding to that molecular formulae. In this article we try to present a simple and innovative method for easy calculation of number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds with the help of 06 (six) new formulae.

Keywords : Open chain olefinic system, cyclic olefinic system, π - and σ -bond, double and single bond, number of carbon and hydrogen atoms.

Introduction

The molecular formula which defines a very large number of chemical structure, in this particular case, it is a herculean task to calculate the nature and number of bonds. Earlier Badertscher *et al.* studied a novel formalism to characterize the degree of unsaturation of organic molecules¹. But no such work has not been taken till now to calculate the number and types of bonds in open chain olefinic system having complex molecular formulae like $C_{176}H_{250}$, $C_{2000}H_{2000}$.

Keeping this in view, a rapid method has been proposed for the calculation of number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds with the help of following 06 (six) completely new formulae for certain aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

Earlier eight new innovative methods including sixteen new formulae have been introduced on the easy prediction of 'Bond-order of mono and diatomic homo and heteronuclear molecules or ions', 'Bond-order of oxide based acid radicals', 'Hybridization', 'IUPAC nomenclature of spiro and bicyclo compounds', 'spin multiplicity value calculation and prediction of magnetic properties of diatomic heteronuclear molecules and ions, 'Aromaticity', 'magnetic properties of homo and heteronuclear diatomic molecules and ions' and 'simultaneous equations as a tool in the spectrophotometric analysis of two non-interacting substances in a binary mixture'²⁻⁹. The present study involves six formulae by just manipulating the number of carbon and hydrogen atoms by using some factors.

We think it would go a long way to help the students of organic chemistry who would choose the subject as their carrier. Experiment *in vitro* on 100 students show that by using these new innovative methods strike rate is 10/10 secs.

On the basis of this, we can strongly recommend that by using these new formulae the students can calculate number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds for aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

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Discussion

(a) For open chain aliphatic hydrocarbons :

Calculation of π -bonds and double bonds (P) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in a given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing double bonds.

The formula to calculate the number of π bonds or double bonds for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is

$$P = [(2X - Y)/2] + 1$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P = number of π bonds/double bonds.

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, $X = 176$, $Y = 250$, therefore $P = (2 \times 176 - 250)/2 + 1 = 51 + 1 = 52$ number of π bonds or double bonds.

Calculation of σ -bonds (S) :

In this case, first we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated hydrocarbon containing double bonds.

The formula to calculate the number of σ bonds for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is

$$S = [X + Y - 1]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S = number of sigma bonds (σ -bonds).

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, $X = 176$, $Y = 250$, therefore $P = 176 + 250 - 1 = 425$ σ bonds.

Calculation of single bonds (A) :

The total number of single bond for an aliphatic straight chain olefin is

$$A = [(3Y/2) - 2]$$

where A = number of single bonds and Y is number of hydrogen atoms.

e.g. : In $C_{176}H_{250}$, $Y = 250$, therefore $A = [(3 \times 250)/2] - 2 = 375 - 2 = 373$ single bonds.

Table 1

Example (C _x H _y)	Straight-chain Structure	π bond/bonds [(2X-Y)/ 2+1]	σ bonds [X+Y-1]	Single bonds [(3Y/2)-2]	Double bond/ bonds [(2X-Y)/ 2+1]
C ₂ H ₄	H ₂ -C=C-H ₂	1	5	4	1
C ₃ H ₆	H ₂ C=CH-CH ₃	1	8	7	1
C ₃ H ₄	H ₂ C=C=CH ₂	2	6	4	2
C ₄ H ₈	(i) H ₂ C=CH-CH ₂ -CH ₃ (ii) H ₃ C-HC=CH-CH ₃	1	11	10	1
C ₄ H ₆	(i) H ₂ C=C=CH-CH ₃ (ii) H ₂ C=CH-CH=CH ₂	2	9	7	2
C ₄ H ₄	H ₂ C=C=C=CH ₂	3	7	4	3
C ₁₇₆ H ₂₅₀	-	52	425	373	52
C ₂₀₀₀ H ₂₀₀₀	-	1001	3999	2998	1001
C ₉₉ H ₄	-	98	102	4	98
C ₂₃ H ₁₂	-	18	34	16	18

(b) For cyclic aliphatic olefinic hydrocarbons :*Calculation of π -bonds and double bonds (P_c) :*

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

The formula to calculate the number of π bonds or double bonds for an aliphatic cyclic olefin is

$$P_c = [(2X - Y)/2]$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and P_c = number of π bonds or double bonds in the cyclic olefinic system.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C₈H₈), $X = Y = 8$, therefore $P_c = 16 - 8/2 = 4$ number of π bonds or double bonds.

Calculation of σ -bonds (S_c) :

In the first case, we have to count the number of carbon atoms (X) and the number of hydrogen atoms (Y) in the given unsaturated cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons.

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The formula to calculate the number of σ bonds for an aliphatic cyclic olefin is

$$S_c = (X + Y)$$

where, X = number of carbon atoms; Y = number of hydrogen atoms and S_c = number of sigma bonds (σ -bonds) in cyclic olefinic system.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C_8H_8), $X = Y = 8$, therefore $S_c = 8 + 8 = 16$ number of σ bonds.

Calculation of single bonds (A_c) :

The total number of single bonds in aliphatic cyclic olefin can be calculated by using the formula $A_c = [3Y/2]$, where A_c = number of single bonds and Y is number of hydrogen atoms in aliphatic cyclic olefin.

e.g. : In cyclooctatetraene (C_8H_8), $Y = 8$, therefore $A_c = 24/2 = 12$ number of single bonds.

Table 2

Example (C_xH_y)	Cycloalkene	π bond/ bonds (P_c)= [(2X-Y)/2]	σ bonds (S_c) [X+Y]	Single bonds (A_c) [(3Y/2)]	Double bond/bonds [(2X-Y)/2]
C_3H_4	Cyclopropene	1	7	6	1
C_4H_4	Cyclobutadiene	2	8	6	2
C_5H_6	Cyclopentadiene	2	11	9	2
C_6H_8	Cyclohexadiene	2	14	12	2
C_7H_8	Cycloheptatriene	3	15	12	3
C_8H_8	Cyclooctatetraene	4	16	12	4

Conclusions

In conclusion here we approach a new rapid innovative method on easier calculation of number of π -bonds, σ -bonds, single and double bonds for aliphatic unsaturated open chain and cyclic olefinic hydrocarbons. This new method is very helpful to undergraduate and graduate level students of chemistry. By using these methods we can easily predict nature of bonds in olefinic system in a very simple and metabolic way.

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